

Short practical guidance on the implementation of record linkage in Germany

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NFDI4Health

National Research Data Infrastructure
for personal health data

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Abstract

Record linkage (RL) is the process of linking data from different sources referring to the same individual. In health research, RL allows for long-term follow-up and the efficient reuse of data, providing insights that would otherwise be unattainable. This guidance document provides a practical introduction to designing RL studies in the context of health research, with a particular focus on the German research landscape.

The document covers crucial aspects of planning an RL study, including defining research question, identifying suitable data sources, assessing legal and technical feasibility, and highlights the importance of early involvement of stakeholders (i.e. legal experts). Emphasis is also placed on data protection, ethical reviews, and documentation. Methodological considerations are discussed, such as different RL techniques (deterministic, probabilistic, gold-standard based), personal identifiers as well as potential error types (false positives, false negatives), and privacy-preserving record linkage (PPRL) techniques. This guidance also provides strategies for ensuring quality assurance and outlines the roles and responsibilities of researchers, data custodians, and Trusted Third Parties (TTPs). It delves into data protection, governance, and legal considerations, addressing compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in Germany and the EU, the necessity of informed consent, and the impact of recent laws like the Health Data Usage Act (GDNG) and the upcoming European Health Data Space (EHDS). Finally, it points to established research data infrastructures such as the NFDI4Health Health Study Hub, NAKO, and Health Data Lab (FDZ Gesundheit) as valuable resources for researchers undertaking RL projects. A checklist and references to supportive software and tools are provided in the appendices to offer practical aid. Overall, the document aims to make RL more accessible, encourage responsible use, and support its broader adoption in health research.

1. Introduction

Record linkage (RL) is the process of linking data from different sources referring to the same individual. In health research, this technique has emerged as a key enabler of long-term follow-ups and efficient data reuse. RL allows researchers to track patient outcomes over time, link individual-level information, and generate novel insights that would not be possible using a single data source.

This guidance document aims to provide researchers with a straightforward introduction and quick overview for planning RL studies in the context of health research. It offers a structured overview of the practical, technical, ethical, and legal dimensions of RL, particularly within the German research landscape. The aim is to make RL more accessible, to demystify key processes, and to encourage wider adoption of responsible record linkage practices. This includes planning an RL study (Section 2), methodological considerations (Section 3), roles and responsibilities (Section 4), data protection, governance and legal considerations (Section 5), established research data infrastructures (Section 6) and final recommendations (Section 7). For convenience, important points to consider are compiled in a checklist (Appendix A) and references to supportive software and tools (Appendix B). For detailed information, readers are referred to the foundational review and guidance by March et al. [1,2] the comprehensive textbook by Christen et al. [3] and the work of Intemann et al. [4], which provides example use cases, a legal overview, and proposals for improving record linkage in Germany. The document does not aim to provide an exhaustive methodological or legal reference. Rather, it serves as an entry point and orientation guide for researchers.

2. Planning a Record Linkage Study

Successful RL begins with rigorous planning. Key steps include defining the research question, identifying relevant data sources, and clarifying the legal and technical feasibility of the chosen linkage approach. Because RL requires personal identifiers, early involvement of legal experts is crucial. Researchers should develop an RL protocol describing the methods, data protection safeguards, and evaluation methods. This should be accompanied, if necessary, by an ethical review. Ideally, collaboration with data holders and Trusted Third Parties (TTPs) should be initiated during the project design phase to avoid subsequent delays. Budgeting for services, e.g. from a TTP and for data management is also essential. To enable external researchers to benefit from a research project, following the FAIR principles will make a study and the created data sources findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable [4].

3. Methodological Considerations

Record Linkage Techniques

The term RL, or data linkage, typically refers to the process of linking two or more datasets at the individual level. The resulting dataset contains merged information from all sources for each person. To realise an RL approach, the source datasets must be **vertically partitioned**, i.e., they must contain different variables describing the same individuals, assuming individuals are in rows and variables in columns. This applies, for example, when linking individual-level study data or cancer registry data with health insurance claims. In contrast, **enriching** datasets with group-level information (e.g., regional unemployment rates) is generally not considered RL. Similarly, **horizontally partitioned** datasets containing the same variables for different individuals, such as datasets from multiple similar studies, are usually combined by stacking and not by linking.

Identifiers and Error Types

The most straightforward linkage method is **deterministic RL** with a shared **direct identifier**, or **unique identifier**, in both datasets. Nordic countries, for example, use a personal identification number for linking health registries [5]. In Germany, such a common unique identifier does not exist for research purposes. In special cases, identifiers like health insurance numbers have been used, such as in the German National Cohort (NAKO) [6,7], but these are always project-related custom solutions.

If no unique identifier is available, researchers must rely on **quasi-identifiers**, variables that allow identification only when used in combination, such as birth date, gender/sex, ZIP code, or surname. However, even combinations of quasi-identifiers may not guarantee unique identification. In a large U.S. database with 80 million individuals, using surname, first name, and date of birth still failed to uniquely identify all persons (chance of false match: 1/108) [8]. Additionally, these variables can contain missing values, are assessed with errors or change over time. For example, a common surname may lead to false positive links, while spelling variations or missing values can lead to false negative links. Therefore, data cleaning and standardisation are critical pre-processing steps before linkage. Nevertheless, errors in linking are commonly present. Two types of RL errors must be distinguished (see Table 1):

	True link	True non-link
Identified as link	Correctly identified link	False link (false positive, homonym error)
Identified as non-link	False non-link (false negative, synonym error)	Correctly identified non-link

Table 1: Classification of record linkage errors

To minimise these errors, various RL algorithms exist, which typically involve a trade-off between both error types.

Linkage Methods

The RL methods can be classified as follows:

1. **Rule-based methods** use simple “if-then” logic (e.g., if name and birth date match, then link).
2. **Distance-based methods** assess similarity scores (e.g., for names or dates) and cluster similar entries (see [3]).
3. **Probabilistic RL**, developed by Newcombe et al. [9] and Fellegi & Sunter [10], assigns match weights based on the likelihood that two entries refer to the same person. The final decision is based on whether the total weight exceeds a pre-defined threshold (see Sayers et al. [11] for a step-by-step guide).
4. **Gold-standard based RL**: if links are known in a subsample, this information can be used to train a prediction model. If generalisation to the whole sample is justified, the prediction model can be used to derive links in the whole sample (for an example see [12]).

To reduce computational burden, **blocking** is often used, that is restricting comparisons to subsets (e.g., only within same ZIP code).

Privacy-Preserving Techniques

Because quasi-identifiers are often personal data, RL requires stringent data protection. Standard practices include separating identifiers from health data, encrypted data transfer, and access controls. In

addition, **Privacy-Preserving Record Linkage (PPRL)** methods have been developed to protect identities during linkage and ensure that the parties involved only receive the information necessary for linkage.

PPRL typically uses encoded identifiers using **hash functions**. While these are deterministic and irreversible, they are not similarity-preserving. This means that even a minor error or variation in the input data will result in a completely different hashed value, preventing a match. To improve privacy, a shared key can be added before hashing. However, if input data contains errors, such hashed values will not match, limiting their usefulness. More advanced techniques such as **Bloom filters** allow for error-tolerant, similarity-preserving linkage (see [13] for details). While offering enhanced privacy, PPRL methods can introduce computational complexities.

Evaluation and Quality Assurance

Every RL project should include a quality assurance plan. Key metrics include:

- False match proportion: % of incorrect links
- Missed match proportion: % of missed correct links
- Positive predictive value: Accuracy of identified matches
- Sensitivity: Proportion of all true matches identified.

These metrics are often only able to be derived if a gold standard is available. If this is not the case, the robustness could be assessed through a sensitivity analysis to see if modifying the linkage approach yields different results. Linked and unlinked subsamples should be compared for possible differences, which could indicate worse linkage quality for certain groups. For example, this could apply to migrants due to name spelling or people who frequently change addresses. Reporting on this investigation enhances transparency. As linkage errors have an influence on the subsequent analysis, these investigations are required to evaluate possible bias in analysis results. Measurement error and misclassification theory could be used to evaluate these biases [14].

4. Roles and Responsibilities

Clear role allocation ensures that data flows are well-managed and compliant. Researchers, data custodians, TTPs, and oversight bodies each have distinct responsibilities. Collaborative governance models can streamline project approvals, ensure data security, and build trust among stakeholders. A data flow diagram can serve as a useful tool for visualising the submission of data, including the sender, format, and recipient.

5. Data Protection, Governance and Legal Considerations

Due to the sensitive nature of health data, RL projects must comply with legal and ethical standards. In Germany and the EU, the General Data Protection Regulation governs data processing, requiring data minimisation, transparency, and purpose limitation. In Germany, RL often requires personal **Informed Consent** (for templates of such documents, please see [15], [16] and [17]) unless exceptions apply under the **Social Code Book** (Sozialgesetzbuch, SGB) or state-level laws (for an overview about legal rules, see [15]). Recent laws such as the **Health Data Usage Act** (Gesundheitsdatennutzungsgesetz, GDNG) will enable project-based linkage of cancer registry and insurance data at the Research Data Hub (Forschungsdatenzentrum Gesundheit). The upcoming European Health Data Space (EHDS) will further harmonise access and governance across EU member states, including secure processing environments and opt-out models.

Data protection best practices include separating identifiers from health data, encrypting all data for submission, and restricting access through role-based controls. This should ensure that the unit performing the linkage only has access to the identifiers and not to the entire analysis data. Similarly, analysts should not receive any information on identifiers (such as names or addresses of patients and participants). The entire process should be documented in a data protection concept. Many RL studies rely on Trusted Third Parties to carry out linkage operations without exposing identifiers to researchers. PPRL techniques further enhance confidentiality by allowing record comparisons on encrypted identifiers.

6. Established Research Data Infrastructures

The **NFDI4Health Health Study Hub** may serve as an efficient starting point for searching for suitable data sources as it ensures findability of health data sources in Germany. It provides data applicants with concise information about RL possibilities with the respective data source (given data holders provided that information). This contains relevant legal regulations, the responsible authority, possible costs, available identifiers, and examples of RL studies with that data source. The Health Study Hub is based on the NFDI4Health metadata schema which covers this information in the record linkage module [18].

From a practical perspective, to foster the reuse of established infrastructures, it is advisable to reuse linked data sources in existing infrastructures, provided they already offer the linked data required to answer the research question, rather than relying on the development of project-specific infrastructures. After all, RL is often only a means to an end and not an end in itself. Two promising examples are (1) the **NAKO** [19] where primary data are linked with cancer registry, health claims, pension insurance and employment office data and (2) the **Health Data Lab** (FDZ Gesundheit) which will link health claims data with cancer registry data according to the GDNG in the future.

7. Final Recommendations

This short compilation of issues to consider shows the complexity researchers face when conducting RL studies. Careful planning, building on developed infrastructures, and available methods will support the implementation of record linking studies. The endeavour of RL studies is offset by a wide range of beneficial investigations that are only possible when different data sources are linked. This guidance document should inform health scientists about practical solutions and provide hands-on advice. The checklist and the reference to software in the appendix provide additional support. Last but not least, to foster reuse and to enable external researchers to benefit from linked data, linkage projects should follow the FAIR principles.

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Appendix A: Checklist

Before Project Start

- Define the research question
- Identify potential data sources using the NFDI4Health Health Study Hub (<https://health-study-hub.de/>)
- Clarify legal and ethical feasibility
- Contact data holders early
- Ensure informed consent and assess legal basis
- Plan the linkage method and quality checks
- Allocate sufficient time, financial, and human resources
- Follow the FAIR principles for the study, data and metadata

Choosing the Right Type of Linkage

- Identify available (quasi-)identifiers
- Check if a unique identifier is available
- Assess whether quasi-identifiers are sufficient
- Consider legal restrictions on sharing identifiers
- Find a method suitable to the research question and considered identifiers
- Evaluate the data quality of identifiers
- Standardise identifiers' formats (e.g., phonetics, date formats)
- Perform data cleaning before linking

Setting Up the Right Tools

- Choose linkage software appropriate to selected method (see Appendix B)
- Ensure tools comply with data protection requirements

Clarifying Stakeholder Roles

- Identify all stakeholders (data holders, researchers, authorities)
- Define responsibilities clearly
- Visualise data flow in a diagram
- Establish communication channels for coordination
- Review legal obligations for each role

Ensuring Data Protection

- Separate identifiers from analysis data
- Encrypt data for transfer
- Apply role-based access control
- Use a Trusted Third Party if required
- Consider privacy-preserving methods (e.g., hashing)
- Develop a data protection concept
- Consider process for archiving and data deletion (e.g., in case of objection)

Ensuring Legal and Ethical Compliance

- Identify the legal basis (e.g., consent, exceptions)
- Obtain informed consent if required (for templates see [15], [16] and [17])
- Consult data protection officers or legal experts
- Conduct a data protection impact assessment if needed
- Seek ethics committee approval if required

Apply data minimisation and purpose limitation principles

Evaluating Linkage Quality

Define quality metrics (e.g., sensitivity)

Compare linkage results with gold standard for validation if available in subsample

Conduct sensitivity analysis

Report methods and results transparently

Established Examples and Research Data Infrastructures

Check whether similar RL projects already exist

Identify their methods and processes

Use established infrastructure if suitable (e.g., from German National Cohort)

Appendix B: Software and Tools

For information on software and tools which can be used in RL projects, please refer to March et al. [1] (pages e25- e26), Christen et al. [3] (pages 379 - 383), and Intemann et al. [7] (page 167).

Literature

1. March S, Antoni M, Kieschke J, Kollhorst B, Maier B, Müller G, . . . Hoffmann F (2018) Quo vadis Datenlinkage in Deutschland? Eine erste Bestandsaufnahme. *Gesundheitswesen* 80 (3):e20-e31. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0043-125070>
2. March S, Andrich S, Drepper J, Horenkamp-Sonntag D, Icks A, Ihle P, . . . Hoffmann F (2020) Good Practice Data Linkage (GPD): A Translation of the German Version. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*:636-650. 10.3390/ijerph17217852
3. Christen P, Ranbaduge T, Schnell R (2020) Linking sensitive data. Springer, Heidelberg. <http://dx.doi.org/10.25646/7847>
4. Wilkinson MD, Dumontier M, Aalbersberg IJ, Appleton G, Axton M, Baak A, . . . Mons B (2016) The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data* 3 (1):1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
5. Sund R, Gissler M (2022) Use of Health Registers. In: Ahrens W, Pigeot I (eds) *Handbook of Epidemiology*. Springer, New York, pp 1-27. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-6625-3_5-1
6. Schipf S, Schöne G, Schmidt B, Günther K, Stübs G, Greiser KH, . . . Ahrens W (2020) Die Basiserhebung der NAKO Gesundheitsstudie: Teilnahme an den Untersuchungsmodulen, Qualitätssicherung und Nutzung von Sekundärdaten. *Bundesgesundheitsblatt - Gesundheitsforschung - Gesundheitsschutz* 63 (3):254-266. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00103-020-03093-z>
7. Intemann T, Kaulke K, Kipker D-K, Lettieri V, Stallmann C, Schmidt CO, . . . Semler SC (2023) White Paper: Verbesserung des Record Linkage für die Gesundheitsforschung in Deutschland. PUBLISSO. <https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006461895>
8. Hillestad R, Bigelow JH, Chaudhry B, Dreyer P, Greenberg MD, Meili R, . . . Taylor R (2008) Identity crisis: an examination of the costs and benefits of a unique patient identifier for the U.S. health care system. <https://www.rand.org/pubs/monographs/MG753.html>. Accessed 10.07.2025
9. Newcombe HB, Kennedy JM, Axford SJ, James AP (1959) Automatic linkage of vital records. *Science* 130 (3381):954-959. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.130.3381.9>
10. Fellegi IP, Sunter AB (1969) A theory for record linkage. *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 64 (328):1183-1210. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1969.10501049>
11. Sayers A, Ben-Shlomo Y, Blom AW, Steele F (2016) Probabilistic record linkage. *International Journal of Epidemiology* 45 (3):954-964. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyv322>

12. Lendle N, Kollhorst B, Intemann T (2025) Exploring the complexity of real-world health data record linkage—an exemplary study linking cancer registry and claims data. *Pharmacoepidemiology and Drug Safety* 34 (4):e70120. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pds.70120>
13. Christen P (2012) A survey of indexing techniques for scalable record linkage and deduplication. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* 24 (9):1537-1555. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TKDE.2011.127>
14. Keogh RH, Shaw PA, Gustafson P, Carroll RJ, Deffner V, Dodd KW, . . . Freedman LS (2020) STRATOS guidance document on measurement error and misclassification of variables in observational epidemiology: Part 1—Basic theory and simple methods of adjustment. *Statistics in Medicine* 39 (16):2197-2231. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sim.8532>
15. Intemann T, Lettieri V, Kipker D-K, Kuntz A, Ahrens W, Pigeot I, . . . Sax U (2023) Informed Consent zum Record Linkage: Best Practice und Mustertexte. PUBLISSO. <https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006399943>
16. AG Consent des Nationalen Steuerungsgremiums der MII des BMBF (2020) Handreichung zur Anwendung der national harmonisierten Patienteninformations- und Einwilligungsdokumente zur Sekundärnutzung von Patientendaten AG Consent der Medizininformatik-Initiative (MII). https://www.medizininformatik-initiative.de/sites/default/files/2020-04/MII_AG-Consent_Handreichung_v0.9d.pdf. Accessed 29.07.2025
17. Arbeitsgruppe Consent (2020) Mustertext Patienteneinwilligung. https://www.medizininformatik-initiative.de/sites/default/files/2020-04/MII_AG-Consent_Einheitlicher-Mustertext_v1.6d.pdf. Accessed 29.07.2025
18. Abaza H, Shutsko A, Klopfenstein SAI, Vorisek CN, Schmidt CO, Brünings-Kuppe C, . . . Golebiewski M (2025) Toward a domain-overarching metadata schema for making health research studies FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable): development of the NFDI4Health Metadata Schema. *JMIR Medical Informatics* 13:e63906. <https://doi.org/10.2196/63906>
19. Peters A, Peters A, Greiser KH, Göttlicher S, Ahrens W, Albrecht M, . . . Zschocke J (2022) Framework and baseline examination of the German National Cohort (NAKO). *European Journal of Epidemiology* 37 (10):1107-1124. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10654-022-00890-5>